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Full Protocol

Title: *A Systematic Review of Fault Tolerance Techniques for Adaptive and Context-aware Systems*

This document consists in a protocol followed over the course of the conduction of our systematic literature review. To establish this protocol, we followed the guidelines for conducting secondary studies proposed by Kitchenham and Charters [1] and Wohlin [2]. Next, we describe how we followed these guidelines to answer the research questions of this study.

Question Formulation

The main goal of this Systematic Literature Review is to identify fault tolerance techniques that have been applied for adaptive systems (ASs) or context-aware systems (CASs) and identify which faults have been mentioned in the literature of fault tolerance that addressed these systems.

Ours research questions were defined as:

RQ1: Which fault tolerance techniques have been proposed for, or applied to, ASs or CASs? This research question aims to provide the reader with an overview of fault tolerance techniques that have been explored within the AS and CAS domains, as well as classifications of techniques that may arise from the analysis of the selected primary studies.

RQ2: Which faults have been identified in ASs or CASs? This research question aims to provide the reader with a list of faults that have been reported in the analysed literature. Beyond this, it intends to lead to a classification of faults that share common characteristics.

Keywords and Synonyms

We used two groups of words to compose the search string:

- Group 1: ("adaptive system" OR "adaptive software" OR "autonomic" OR "context-aware" OR "context-awareness" OR "self-adaptive" OR "self organising")
- Group 2: ("fault tolerance" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

Base Search String

("adaptive system" OR "adaptive systems" OR "adaptive software" OR "autonomic" OR "context-aware" OR "context aware" OR "context-awareness" OR "context awareness" OR "self-adaptive" OR "self adaptive" OR "self-organising" OR "self organising" OR "self-organizing" OR "self organizing") AND ("fault tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

Selection of sources

We selected traditional repositories of scientific literature in the field of Computer Science. Besides that, the Google Scholar engine was included to apply the snowballing techniques.

List of Selected Sources:

- IEEE Xplore;
- Elsevier Science Direct;
- Wiley;
- ACM Digital Library;
- SpringerLink;
- Scopus;
- Web of Science;
- Google Scholar (for snowballing);

We narrowed the search to title, summary and keywords fields, except for the Springer SpringerLink search engine that only allowed for narrowing the search to the title and summary fields. Furthermore, due to the large number of studies retrieved with Springer SpringerLink and Elsevier Scopus, we applied a filter by Computer Science and Engineering areas. Due to the hybrid characteristic of some search engines, some studies may be recovered by more than one search engine, so we filtered the duplicate studies. Additional databases were also sources of primary studies because we applied the snowballing process.

Process of searching for studies

The process of selection of studies was performed in 3 steps, as follows:

Step 1 - Automatic search: in this phase, a string was created with words related to the research area. The string passed by customisation for each search engine and was submitted in the search engines and the studies were stored for later analysis.

Step 2 - Snowballing backward: the snowballing backward technique was applied to the

set of articles selected in step 2. For each selected study, we did an analysis of its list of references in order to identify other studies of interest.

Step 3 - Snowballing forward: we applied the snowballing forward technique to the set of articles selected in step 2. For each selected study, we did an analysis of the studies that cited it using Google Scholar.

Study Selection Process

We defined inclusion and exclusion criteria for study selection.

Inclusion Criteria (I):

- (I1) The study either proposes or applies a fault tolerance technique to SAs or CASs;
- (I2) The study is a primary and peer-reviewed study published either in a journal or in conference/workshop proceedings;

A study is selected if it passes in (I1 AND I2).

Exclusion Criteria (E):

- (E1) The study proposes or applies a technique to recover the software from failures caused by malicious attacks;
- (E2) The study is not written in English;

Studies that fall into at least one of the above criteria are not selected. The process of selection of studies was performed in four phases, as follows:

Phase 1: Duplicate study filtering: as a result of the automatic search, a study may have been retrieved by more than one repository, thus generating duplicate entries. In this step we filtered and excluded the duplicate studies. Thus, the remaining studies were submitted to phase 2.

Phase 2: Initial selection of studies: during this phase, we read the title and summary of each study and applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria in order to check if it should be selected for full reading.

Phase 3: Final selection of studies: during this phase we performed the full reading of the studies from phase 2. We applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria to decide if the study would be part of the final set studies.

Phase 4: Identifying overlappings: After analysing the studies, we identified overlaps

among them. This includes studies that are either updated or improved by their authors and subsume the previous ones.

Data Extraction and Data Classification

The data extraction was performed using the StArt [3] tool and the data was stored in customised forms. The tool supported the process of selection of studies and filling out of the extraction form. General information, such as, title, authors and year of publication were collected to compose the list of references. After the extraction, we analysed the studies and classified them according to the type of research, as follows:

- (i) evaluation research: the solution was used in practice and an empirical evaluation was accomplished;
- (ii) validation research: the solution has not yet been used in practice; this research type uses an empirical evaluation, which can be: simulation as an empirical method, laboratory experiments (machine or human), academic case study (e.g. with students), etc;
- (iii) solution proposal: it proposes a solution and presents a small example as a proof of concept;
- (iv) philosophical papers: it presents a conceptual framework;
- (v) opinion papers: it presents the authors' opinion about something;
- (vi) experience papers: it presents the authors' personal experience and it contains a list of lessons learned.

We classified the studies according to the type of publication venue (namely, journal, conference or workshop). We also identified the faults mentioned in the studies, analysed its characteristics and classified them in generic faults. The data extraction and classification were performed by the same researcher.

Additional Information

The data extraction fields was defined as:

1. A summary of the study;
2. The fault tolerance technique applied and its characteristics;
3. Faults mentioned by the study;
4. Challenges in the application of fault tolerance or in the guarantee of dependability in SAs and CASs;
5. Type of the study (e.g. validation research, solution proposal, etc);
6. Type of venue of publication;

7. Date of publication;
8. Peer-review information;

REFERENCES

[1] B. Kitchenham and S. Charters. Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering. Technical Report (EBSE) 2007-001, Keele University and Durham University Joint Report, UK, 2007.

[2] C. Wohlin. Guidelines for snowballing in systematic literature studies and a replication in software engineering. In Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE), pages 1–10. ACM Press, 2014.

[3] E. Hernandez, A. Zamboni, S. Fabbri and A. A. D. Thommazo. Using gqm and tam to evaluate start - a tool that supports systematic review. CLEI Electronic Journal, vol. 15, pp. 3–3, 2012.